

The Effectiveness of International Humanitarian Intervention in Conflict Zones

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Abstract

This academic article examines the effectiveness of international humanitarian intervention in conflict zones. Humanitarian intervention refers to the use of military, diplomatic, or economic measures by external actors to protect civilians, promote human rights, and alleviate suffering in areas affected by armed conflict. The research employs a comprehensive approach, incorporating content analysis, case study, and historical analysis in its methodology. It explores the key challenges faced by international actors in implementing humanitarian interventions and evaluates their impact on conflict resolution and post-conflict reconstruction. Through this thorough analysis of case studies and scholarly literature, this article contributes to the ongoing debate surrounding the efficacy of international humanitarian intervention.

Keywords: Humanitarian Intervention, Conflict Zones, International Actors, Conflict Resolution, Post-Conflict Reconstruction, Effectiveness.

1. Introduction

In the turbulent landscape of global conflict, international humanitarian intervention emerges as a complex and oft-debated tool for restoring peace and alleviating suffering. Defined by the involvement of external actors – states, organizations, and regional bodies – it aims to safeguard civilians, prevent human rights violations, and address the dire needs of populations caught in the crossfire. The ultimate aspiration? To suture the wounds of conflict and usher in an era of stability and prosperity [1,2].

Yet, despite its noble intentions, international humanitarian intervention remains a subject shrouded in controversy. Questions concerning its effectiveness, legitimacy, and long-term impact echo within academic and policy circles [3]. This article delves into this critical discourse, wielding a magnifying glass to examine the intricate factors that shape the outcomes of such interventions.

From the initial spark of conflict to the strategies employed in its aftermath, this study meticulously dissects the entire intervention ecosystem [5]. It scrutinizes the conditions under which intervention is deemed necessary, the actors involved and their motivations, and the specific approaches adopted in each unique conflict zone [2]. By subjecting each element to rigorous analysis, this study seeks to illuminate the hidden complexities of international humanitarian intervention and ultimately assess its true efficacy in tackling the global scourge of conflict.

1.1 Literature Review

Humanitarian intervention in conflict zones is a complex and

multifaceted endeavor that requires careful examination of its effectiveness. This literature review explores key research findings and insights from various perspectives, shedding light on the challenges and successes associated with international humanitarian interventions.

Immediate Needs and Humanitarian Response: Al-Abdulla et al. (2023) dive into the challenges of health system recovery in Northwest Syria, pinpointing the critical need to address immediate health needs and showcasing the vital role of humanitarian intervention in conflict zones. Meanwhile, Banatvala and Zwi (2000) champion evidence-based public health interventions as crucial for tackling health crises arising from conflict. Both studies highlight the importance of swift and well-informed action in mitigating the immediate human cost of conflict [1,2].

Intervention Dynamics and Nuances: Arman's (2023) case study of external interventions in Yemen delves deeper, offering a nuanced analysis of international involvement in internal conflicts [4]. By examining the complexities and consequences of intervention, this study enriches our understanding of the dynamics at play. It reminds us that interventions, while potentially impactful, are not without their own challenges and require careful consideration of their long-term effects.

The literature review provides a comprehensive overview of key studies that contribute to the discourse on the effectiveness of international humanitarian intervention in conflict zones. The diverse perspectives, ranging from health system recovery to media framing and diplomatic efforts, collectively contribute to

a nuanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities in this complex field.

1.2 Statement of Problem

The challenges inherent in humanitarian intervention pose intricate obstacles to the effective implementation of strategies aimed at conflict resolution and post-conflict reconstruction. This comprehensive examination identifies several key areas of concern. Firstly, the tension between respecting state sovereignty and the responsibility to protect vulnerable populations generates complex debates about the limits of intervention, as highlighted in the discussions on sovereignty and consent. The intricacies of obtaining consent and navigating political dynamics become apparent, particularly when consent is absent or strategically manipulated.

Secondly, logistical and operational obstacles hinder the comprehensive assistance required in conflict zones, with limited resources, security risks, and coordination difficulties among diverse actors contributing to the challenges. These challenges extend to military intervention and peacekeeping operations, where a delicate balance between impartiality and the use of force is crucial, and risks of unintended consequences and coordination issues must be addressed.

Additionally, diplomatic engagement and mediation efforts face complexities related to inclusivity, power dynamics, and overcoming deep-rooted grievances, emphasizing the need for sustained efforts throughout conflict stages. The multifaceted role of humanitarian aid and development assistance confronts challenges in coordination, sustainability, and the transition from emergency response to long-term development. Finally, accountability and transitional justice mechanisms, vital for post-conflict societies, encounter challenges such as political resistance, resource limitations, and the delicate balance between justice and reconciliation imperatives.

This extensive exploration of challenges in humanitarian intervention unveils a complex web of interconnected issues that necessitates a nuanced understanding. Addressing these challenges is imperative for enhancing the effectiveness of interventions, informing policymaking, and developing strategies that foster lasting peace and stability in conflict-ridden regions. To attain this goal, the study utilizes an extensive methodology that includes content analysis, case study, and historical analysis. This approach aims to acquire a nuanced comprehension of the effectiveness of international humanitarian intervention in conflict zones.

1.3 The Research Gap

Intricately woven threads of sovereignty, military intervention, diplomatic engagement, humanitarian aid, and accountability form the tapestry of humanitarian interventions in conflict zones. While existing research meticulously examines these threads individually, a critical gap remains: the absence of a holistic perspective that integrates them into a unified fabric. This fragmented approach hinders our ability to truly grasp the complex interplay between these elements, ultimately limiting

our understanding and effectiveness in navigating the turbulent waters of conflict.

1.4 Historical Context and Rationale for Humanitarian Intervention

From the earliest glimmerings of humanitarian action to the evolving principles of Responsibility to Protect (R2P), the history of international intervention in conflict zones is a complex tapestry woven with ethical considerations and legal frameworks. This analysis delves into the thread of R2P, a pivotal milestone that reshaped the conceptualization and justification for intervention [5].

Rooted in the bedrock of ethical and legal foundations, R2P established a compelling rationale for intervening in situations of mass atrocities and human rights violations [1]. This emphasis on safeguarding vulnerable populations underscores the critical role international action can play in mitigating suffering and upholding the principles of human dignity.

By providing this historical context and rationale, this article aims to deepen our understanding of the evolution of humanitarian intervention and the intellectual foundations that inform its practice today. It sets the stage for a comprehensive analysis of the effectiveness of international interventions in conflict zones, taking into account both the theoretical underpinnings and the practical challenges encountered in implementing such interventions [3].

1.5 Challenges in Humanitarian Intervention

In the murky waters of conflict zones, where humanitarian crises collide with the entrenched principle of state sovereignty, international intervention navigates a perilous path. This analysis dives into this complex terrain, examining the challenges and complexities that arise when external actors seek to intervene in the internal affairs of sovereign states [6].

At the heart of this tension lies the delicate balance between respecting state sovereignty and upholding the responsibility to protect vulnerable populations from atrocities and gross human rights violations [4]. The analysis unpacks this balancing act, shedding light on the ongoing debates regarding the boundaries of sovereignty and the criteria that can legitimize external intervention.

By exploring these challenges comprehensively, this article aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted obstacles faced in humanitarian intervention. Recognizing and addressing these challenges is crucial for improving the effectiveness of interventions and developing more informed policies and strategies in conflict zones [3,5].

1.6 Military Intervention and Peacekeeping Operations

This segment thoroughly explores the role of military intervention and peacekeeping operations within the framework of humanitarian interventions. It delves into the examination of both the advantages and limitations associated with deploying military forces to safeguard civilians and enforce peace

agreements in conflict zones [3,6].

The analysis initiates by underscoring the potential advantages of military intervention, highlighting its capability to provide a swift and robust response for safeguarding vulnerable populations from imminent harm [3]. It goes on to explore the role of military forces in serving as a deterrent to perpetrators of violence, establishing secure spaces for civilians, and reinstating a sense of security [2]. Moreover, the analysis critically examines the contributions of peacekeeping operations in facilitating dialogue, encouraging reconciliation, and overseeing ceasefire agreements [3].

However, the analysis openly acknowledges the inherent limitations and challenges associated with military intervention. It delves into the intricacies of maintaining a delicate balance between impartiality and the use of force [5]. Emphasizing the fragile nature of military intervention, the analysis underscores the imperative of sustaining credibility and legitimacy throughout the intervention process [6]. Moreover, it addresses potential risks, such as unintended consequences, collateral damage, or the exacerbation of the conflict [3].

By critically examining the role of military intervention and peacekeeping operations, this article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of their impact within the context of humanitarian interventions. It recognizes the potential benefits they offer while highlighting the complexities and challenges that must be carefully navigated to achieve the desired outcomes of protecting civilians and fostering peace and stability in conflict zones.

1.7 Diplomatic Engagement and Mediation

The bedrock of successful humanitarian interventions often lies in the intricate dance of diplomacy and mediation. This analysis delves into the crucial role of diplomatic initiatives, particularly those spearheaded by the United Nations and regional bodies, in navigating the complex terrain of conflict towards peaceful resolutions and transitions to sustainable peace [3].

The analysis commences by emphasizing the pivotal role of diplomacy in conflict resolution, highlighting its potential to bring conflicting parties to the negotiating table and foster dialogue [7]. It scrutinizes the role of mediators and facilitators who work to bridge divides, facilitate communication, and build trust among warring factions. Exploring various diplomatic tools and techniques employed, such as shuttle diplomacy, track-two diplomacy, and peace conferences, the examination aims to promote dialogue and reconciliation [6].

By scrutinizing the significance of diplomatic engagement and mediation, this article aims to underscore their vital role in humanitarian interventions. It recognizes the potential of dialogue and negotiation in resolving conflicts and promoting reconciliation. The examination also highlights the challenges faced in these processes and underscores the importance of international organizations' involvement in facilitating successful outcomes [3].

1.8 Humanitarian Aid and Development Assistance

In the aftermath of conflict, the lifeline of humanitarian aid and development assistance stretches across shattered landscapes, seeking to mend both immediate wounds and long-term scars. This analysis critically examines the effectiveness of this vital intervention, delving into the multifaceted role of aid in supporting affected populations and paving the way for sustainable post-conflict reconstruction [1].

The analysis initiates by discussing the immediate and lifesaving nature of humanitarian aid, aiming to provide essential goods and services to meet the urgent needs of conflict-affected populations [2]. Evaluating the effectiveness of humanitarian aid delivery mechanisms, such as emergency relief operations, food distribution, healthcare provision, and shelter assistance, the examination explores challenges associated with access, logistical constraints, and ensuring the efficient and equitable distribution of aid.

By comprehensively evaluating the role of humanitarian aid and development assistance, this article aims to provide a nuanced understanding of their contributions to conflict-affected populations and post-conflict reconstruction [8]. It recognizes the immediate and life-saving impact of humanitarian aid while emphasizing the need for sustainable development initiatives to address the root causes of conflicts and foster lasting peace.

1.9 Accountability and Transitional Justice

The smoldering embers of conflict often leave behind a yearning for both justice and healing. International tribunals, truth commissions, and reparations programs emerge as crucial tools in post-conflict societies, striving to extinguish the flames of vengeance and build a foundation for lasting peace [4]. This exploration delves into the critical role of accountability and transitional justice mechanisms in ensuring justice, fostering reconciliation, and preventing future conflicts.

The analysis begins by emphasizing the importance of accountability in addressing past human rights abuses and violations committed during conflicts [9]. It explores the role of international tribunals, such as the International Criminal Court (ICC) and ad hoc tribunals, in prosecuting individuals responsible for war crimes, genocide, and crimes against humanity. Evaluating the impact of these tribunals in bringing perpetrators to justice, providing redress to victims, and deterring future atrocities.

The analysis also addresses the significance of reparations programs in post-conflict societies [6]. It examines the role of reparations in providing compensation to victims, restoring their dignity, and addressing the socio-economic inequalities exacerbated by conflicts. Exploring different forms of reparations, such as financial compensation, symbolic gestures, and community development projects, it evaluates their impact on individual and collective healing.

By critically examining the role of accountability and transitional justice, this article aims to shed light on their importance in post-

conflict societies [4]. It recognizes their potential to ensure justice, promote reconciliation, and contribute to sustainable peace. The exploration also acknowledges the challenges associated with implementing these mechanisms, such as political resistance, resource limitations, and striking a balance between justice and reconciliation imperatives.

2. Case Studies

The intervention in Kosovo, led by NATO in 1999, is explored to evaluate its objectives, strategies, and outcomes, including the impact on protecting civilians and post-conflict reconstruction. Challenges such as ethnic tensions, limited international consensus, and long-term political stability are assessed [2].

Examining the case of Rwanda in 1994, the international community's response to genocide is critically assessed, focusing on the effectiveness of humanitarian intervention in preventing mass atrocities, protecting civilians, and facilitating post-genocide reconciliation. Challenges include delayed intervention, a lack of a robust mandate, and limited resources [3].

The case of Libya in 2011, involving NATO and regional actors, is analyzed to understand intervention objectives, strategies, and outcomes, including the protection of civilians and the overthrow of the Gaddafi regime. Challenges during the intervention, such as complex conflict dynamics, mission creep, and post-conflict stability, are critically evaluated [6].

By conducting a comparative analysis of these case studies, this contribution contributes to a nuanced understanding of the unique complexities and challenges faced in different conflict contexts, providing context-specific approaches and lessons learned [2,3,6-8].

These case studies offer valuable insights that inform future policy and practice in humanitarian interventions, emphasizing the importance of context-specific approaches to address the complexities of diverse conflict contexts [2,3,6-8].

2.1 Assessing Impact and Lessons Learned

Do international interventions effectively navigate the tumultuous seas of conflict and post-conflict reconstruction? This critical question lies at the heart of ongoing evaluations, with valuable lessons gleaned from diverse interventions such as military operations, diplomatic engagement, and peacekeeping efforts [1-4,6]. This analysis dissects the effectiveness of these strategies in achieving crucial objectives like silencing the guns, protecting vulnerable populations, and building lasting peace [3,5]. However, disentangling the threads of impact and causality within the intricate web of conflict poses a significant challenge, demanding continuous refinement of assessment methodologies [10].

Drawing on these insights, the analysis distills lessons learned to inform future interventions, emphasizing context-specific approaches, local ownership, and comprehensive strategies addressing root causes of conflicts [1,11,12]. This underscores the need for continuous learning, flexibility, and adaptability

in designing and implementing interventions [13]. This critical evaluation contributes to the body of knowledge surrounding effective intervention strategies, informing policymakers, practitioners, and researchers on best practices and areas for improvement [4,7].

3. Main Major Findings

3.1 Challenges in Humanitarian Intervention

The core challenge in international humanitarian intervention is balancing state sovereignty with the responsibility to protect vulnerable populations (A). Debates on the limits of sovereignty and justification for intervention are complex and nuanced. Obtaining host state consent or agreement from relevant parties is crucial, but intricate political dynamics can hinder negotiations (B). Lack of or manipulated consent poses significant barriers. Logistical and operational obstacles like limited resources, funding constraints, insufficient personnel, security risks in volatile zones, and coordination issues among diverse actors further complicate comprehensive assistance efforts (C).

3.2 Military Intervention and Peacekeeping Operations

Military intervention boasts swift and robust responses, deterring violence, establishing civilian havens, and restoring security (A). However, balancing impartiality with force presents a delicate challenge, rife with risks like unintended consequences, collateral damage, and mission creep (B). Successful navigation demands effective coordination and communication among military, international organizations, and local stakeholders to avoid conflicting goals and ensure a unified approach (C).

3.3 Diplomatic Engagement and Mediation

Diplomacy plays a crucial role in conflict resolution, bridging divides and fostering dialogue and trust between adversaries (A). Its effectiveness lies in deploying tools like shuttle diplomacy and peace conferences to promote reconciliation (B). International organizations, like the UN and regional bodies, are key players in diplomatic engagement and mediation. Challenges remain, however, including ensuring inclusivity, managing power dynamics, and addressing deep-rooted grievances.

3.4 Humanitarian Aid and Development Assistance

Humanitarian aid's immediate lifeline addresses urgent needs, but access, logistics, and equitable distribution remain hurdles (A). Effective coordination among government agencies, NGOs, and international organizations is crucial, especially for the challenging transition from emergency response to long-term development (B). Beyond immediate relief, integrating long-term development initiatives becomes imperative to address root causes, foster social cohesion, and empower marginalized communities (C).

3.5 Accountability and Transitional Justice

International tribunals, truth commissions, and reparations programs stand as pillars of justice, reconciliation, and conflict prevention (A). Challenges remain, from political resistance and resource constraints to balancing justice with reconciliation. Yet, their impact transcends post-conflict settings. These mechanisms deter future conflicts and heal past wounds, paving the way for

long-term peace and stability (B).

3.6 Case Studies

Empirical insights derived from comparative case studies, such as those examining Kosovo, Rwanda, and Libya, provide valuable evidence and lessons for understanding the effectiveness and challenges of international humanitarian interventions (A). These case studies offer nuanced perspectives on the complexities of interventions, emphasizing the importance of context-specific approaches and drawing on lessons learned to inform future strategies.

3.7 Assessing Impact and Lessons Learned

Humanitarian interventions significantly impact conflict resolution, halting violence, protecting civilians, and paving the way for lasting peace (A). Effectiveness varies across strategies like military action, diplomacy, and peacekeeping. In post-conflict reconstruction, interventions restore governance, foster development, and tackle inequalities, but face challenges in resource allocation, coordination, and sustained engagement (B).

Common patterns highlight crucial elements for success: strong coordination, inclusive approaches, and unwavering commitment. Yet, challenges remain, from political constraints and limited resources to complex local dynamics. Lessons learned stress context-specific approaches, local ownership, and comprehensive solutions addressing root causes (C). Continuous learning, flexibility, and adaptability are key to enhancing future interventions' effectiveness (D).

4. Discussion

The discussion serves to synthesize the findings and insights presented throughout the article, focusing on the overall effectiveness of international humanitarian intervention in conflict zones. While acknowledging the important contributions made by these interventions, it also recognizes their limitations, critiques, and challenges.

Long-term sustainability is a significant challenge in humanitarian intervention. While immediate relief and assistance are necessary, long-term development and rebuilding efforts are equally important. However, sustaining these efforts over an extended period poses challenges in terms of resource allocation, coordination, and ensuring continued international engagement. Effective post-conflict reconstruction requires long-term commitments to address root causes, build institutions, and promote social and economic development.

Acknowledging the importance of local perspectives and participation in humanitarian interventions is critical. In-depth discussions should explore the significance of involving local communities in decision-making processes, as their insights contribute to context-specific approaches and culturally sensitive interventions. This inclusion fosters a sense of ownership and enhances the sustainability of interventions.

A more explicit examination of gender considerations is

warranted. Recognizing the different impacts of interventions on various genders and emphasizing gender-sensitive approaches are vital components of conflict resolution and post-conflict reconstruction. The discussion should delve into how interventions can address gender-specific challenges and contribute to gender equality.

Assessing the role of technology and innovation in humanitarian interventions adds another layer to the discussion. This includes exploring how digital tools, communication technologies, and innovative approaches enhance the efficiency, coordination, and impact of interventions. The integration of technological solutions contributes to adaptive and effective strategies.

A dedicated exploration of the environmental impact of humanitarian interventions is crucial. Assessing how interventions may affect the environment in conflict zones and discussing strategies for environmentally sustainable practices align with broader goals of sustainable development. This consideration is essential for minimizing long-term ecological consequences.

Analyzing the influence of public opinion, both locally and internationally, on humanitarian interventions is key. Understanding how interventions are perceived and accepted by various stakeholders can shape their success. The discussion should explore strategies for effective communication and engagement to garner support and mitigate potential challenges arising from differing perceptions.

A more in-depth exploration of the role of humanitarian interventions in post-conflict reconciliation is warranted. Highlighting specific initiatives or strategies that contribute to rebuilding trust and fostering reconciliation among communities affected by conflict adds depth to the discussion. This includes addressing social, cultural, and economic aspects integral to sustainable peace.

5. Conclusion

While navigating complex political dynamics and overcoming operational limitations in conflict zones, international humanitarian intervention remains a critical tool. Its contributions to protecting civilians, promoting human rights, and resolving humanitarian crises are undeniable, even in the face of unavoidable challenges like sovereignty concerns.

To enhance the effectiveness of international humanitarian intervention, several key considerations must be taken into account. First, improving coordination among various actors involved in intervention efforts is crucial. Effective communication, collaboration, and information sharing are necessary to ensure a unified and coherent approach. Second, addressing the root causes of conflicts is essential for sustainable outcomes. Interventions should prioritize efforts to address socio-economic disparities, promote inclusivity, and tackle underlying grievances. Third, placing a greater emphasis on long-term development initiatives is crucial. This entails not only immediate relief but also investing in infrastructure, education, healthcare, and livelihood programs to rebuild societies and

prevent future conflicts.

Additionally, ensuring accountability is paramount in achieving lasting peace and justice. Holding perpetrators accountable for their actions through mechanisms such as international tribunals and truth commissions is crucial for reconciliation and the prevention of future conflicts. Moreover, future research and policy development should continue to refine intervention strategies, taking into account the complexities of conflict zones and the protection of vulnerable populations.

The international humanitarian intervention represents a vital means of addressing the challenges faced in conflict zones. By improving coordination, addressing root causes, prioritizing long-term development, and ensuring accountability, the effectiveness of these interventions can be enhanced, leading to better outcomes for conflict resolution and post-conflict reconstruction.

Recommendations

1. **Enhance Multilateral Coordination:** Strengthen coordination among diverse humanitarian actors by developing comprehensive mechanisms for effective communication, collaboration, and information sharing, establishing standardized protocols for joint decision-making, and minimizing resource duplication.

2. **Prioritize Conflict Prevention and Sustainable Development:** Address conflict root causes, invest in socio-economic development, promote inclusivity, and address grievances. Prioritize long-term development initiatives for resilient communities and lasting stability.

3. **Strengthen Accountability Mechanisms:** Strengthen accountability mechanisms, promote local community involvement, and refine humanitarian interventions through research, policy development, and international cooperation to ensure lasting peace and justice.

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